

Modified Regression-Cum-Dual Mean Imputation Schemes for Estimating Population Mean Under Two-Phase Simple Random Sampling

By

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ABSTRACT

In this research, It has been paramount for many researchers under sample survey to use auxiliary information incorporation with the study variables in an estimation stage to modify estimator in order to increase the precision of the estimated population mean. This research work proposed modified regression-cum-dual mean imputation schemes for estimating population mean under two-phase simple random sampling.it concluded that the modified estimators demonstrated a high level of efficiency over the existing estimators considered for both case one and two..

Keywords: *Auxiliary variable*, Population Mean, Mean Squared Errors (MSE) and Bias

1.0 Introduction

Sampling theory is the field of statistics that is concerned with the collection, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from sampling the population under study. The application of sampling theory is concerned not only with the proper selection of observations from the auxiliary variable. Many prominent authors developed several modified and improved ratio, regression, and exponential type estimators by using the population information of the auxiliary variable x . However, the information about the population mean of the auxiliary variable is not always available. In the environment mentioned above, the most popular sampling scheme is

the two-phase sampling scheme which was first established by Neyman (1938) to accumulate information on sampling. It is customarily acquired when the accumulation of information on a study variable is very costly but relatively cheaper to accumulate information on auxiliary variables that are correlated with the study variables. Due to these reasons, the two-phase sampling becomes a powerful and cost-effective scheme for obtaining the authentic estimate in the one-phase sample for the unknown parameters of the auxiliary variable. Authors like Kumar and Bahl (2006), Singh and Vishwakarma (2007), Singh (2011), Ozgul and Cingi (2014), Kalita *et al.* (2016), Noor-Al-Amin *et al.* (2016), Bazad and Bazad (2019), Bhushan and Gupta (2019), Adamu *et al.* (2019) and Bhushan *et al.* (2023) have extensively worked under two-phase sampling. However, the applicability of the aforementioned estimators depends on the complete availability of sample information measured on both the study and auxiliary variables. Reduction in the sizes of sample information due to non-response decreases the efficiency of these estimators. In literature, Sukhatme (1962), Choudhury and Singh (2015), Audu and Adewara (2017a,b), Adamu *et al.* (2019) investigated the classical ratio estimator in two-phase sampling. Following Srivenkataraman (1980), Kumar and Bahl (2006) envisaged a class of dual to exponential type ratio estimators using two phases. Singh and Vishwakarma (2007) investigated Bahl and Tuteja's (1991) exponential ratio and product estimators of population mean under two-phase sampling. Singh (2011), Ozgul and Cingi (2014) developed a class of exponential regression cum ratio estimator in two-phase sampling. Kalita *et al.* (2016) suggested exponential ratio-cum-exponential dual-to-ratio estimators using two-phase sampling. Following Kumar and Bahl (2006) and Kalita *et al.* (2016), Bazad and Bazad (2019) developed some classes of dual-to-ratio exponential-type estimators. Bhushan and Gupta (2019) provided some log-type estimators of population mean using two-phase sampling.

Zaman and Kadilar (2021a) introduced a new class of exponential estimators for finite population mean in two-phase sampling whereas Zaman and Kadilar (2021b) examined an exponential ratio and product estimators of population mean under two-phase sampling. Bhushan *et al.* (2021a) suggested some efficient classes of estimators. Bhushan *et al.* (2021b) developed some efficient classes of estimators under two-phase sampling. Recently, Bhushan and Kumar (2023) suggested a new efficient class of estimators of population mean using two-phase sampling.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Some Existing Estimators under SRSWOR

The contributions of Cochran (1942), Deming (1956), Hurvitz (1952) and others helped in laying the foundation of modern sampling theory. The work done during these periods made important contribution to the modern sampling theory by suggesting methods of utilizing the auxiliary information for the purpose of estimation of the population mean in order to increase the precision of the estimates.

To discuss some of the developed estimators in literature based on auxiliary variables, the following descriptions about the population and sample units were considered.

Let $\Omega = (1, 2, 3 \dots N)$ be a population of size N and Y, X be two real valued functions having values $(Y_i, X_i) \in \mathbb{R}^+$ on the i^{th} unit of $U(1 = i = N)$. Let \bar{Y} and \bar{X} be the population means of Y and X respectively with C_y and C_x as coefficients of variation of Y and X .

Let a pair (y_i, x_i) of simple random sample of size n be drawn without replacement from the population $\Omega = (1, 2, 3, \dots, N)$ and \bar{y}, \bar{x} be sample means based on the sample drawn.

The usual sample mean \bar{y} , traditional ratio estimator \bar{y}_r (Cochran, 1942), product estimator \bar{y}_p (Murthy, 1964) and Dual to ratio estimator \bar{y}_{st} (Strivenkataramana, 1980) with their respective bias and variance/mean square error are defined as

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{var}(\bar{y}) = \frac{1-f}{n} \bar{Y}^2 C_y^2 \quad (2.2)$$

$$\bar{y}_r = \frac{\bar{y}}{\bar{x}} \bar{X} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\text{Bias}(\bar{y}_r) = \bar{Y} \frac{1-f}{n} [C_x^2 - \rho_{xy} C_x C_y] \quad (2.4)$$

$$\text{MSE}(\bar{y}_r) = \bar{Y}^2 \frac{1-f}{n} [C_y^2 + C_x^2 - 2\rho_{xy} C_x C_y] \quad (2.5)$$

$$\bar{y}_p = \frac{\bar{y}}{\bar{X}} \bar{x} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\text{Bias}(\bar{y}_p) = \bar{Y} \frac{1-f}{n} [C_x^2 + \rho_{xy} C_x C_y] \quad (2.7)$$

$$\text{MSE}(\bar{y}_p) = \bar{Y}^2 \frac{1-f}{n} [C_y^2 + C_x^2 + 2\rho_{xy} C_x C_y] \quad (2.8)$$

$$\bar{y}_{st} = \bar{y} \frac{N\bar{X} - n\bar{x}}{(N-n)\bar{X}} \quad (2.9)$$

$$Bias(\bar{y}_{st}) = \bar{Y} \frac{1-f}{n} \left[\left(\frac{n}{N-n} \right)^2 C_x^2 - \frac{n}{N-n} \rho_{xy} C_x C_y \right] \quad (2.10)$$

$$MSE(\bar{y}_{st}) = \bar{Y}^2 \frac{1-f}{n} \left[C_y^2 + \left(\frac{n}{N-n} \right)^2 C_x^2 - 2 \frac{n}{N-n} \rho_{xy} C_x C_y \right] \quad (2.11)$$

Where $f = \frac{n}{N}$, $f^* = \frac{n}{n_1}$, $f_1 = \frac{n_1}{N}$, $f^{**} = \frac{1-f}{n} + \frac{1-f_1}{n_1}$, $C_{yx} = \rho_{xy} C_y / C_x$, $C_{yz} = \rho_{yz} C_y / C_z$,

$$C_{xz} = \rho_{xz} C_x / C_z.$$

The traditional ratio estimator \bar{y}_r and Dual to ratio estimator \bar{y}_{st} have higher efficiencies when the correlation between the study and auxiliary variables is strong and positive while product estimator \bar{y}_p has higher efficiency when the correlation between the study and auxiliary variables is strong and negative.

For estimating the population mean \bar{Y} of the study variate y , Singh and Espejo (2003) considered a linear combination of ratio and product estimators' type given by

$$\bar{y}_{RP} = \bar{y} \left[k \frac{\bar{X}}{\bar{x}} + (1-k) \frac{\bar{x}}{\bar{X}} \right] \quad (2.12) \text{ and obtained that estimator attained optimality when}$$

$k = \frac{(1+C)}{2}$ with $C = C_y/C_x$, where C_y is the coefficient of variation of y and C_x is the coefficient of variation of x .

Singh and Espejo (2007), modified that when the population mean \bar{X} of x is not known, a first-phase sample of size n_1 should be drawn from the population on which only the x -characteristic is measured in order to furnish a good estimate of \bar{X} . Then a second-phase sample of size n is drawn on which both the variables y and x are measured. Let $\bar{x}_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} x_i$ denote the sample

mean of x based on the first-phase sample of size n_1 , Singh and Espejo (2007) considered a ratio-product type estimator in the two-phase sampling given by

$$\bar{y}_{RP}^{(d)} = \bar{y} \left[k \frac{\bar{x}_1}{\bar{x}} + (1-k) \frac{\bar{x}}{\bar{x}_1} \right] \quad (2.13)$$

Choudhury and Singh (2012) consider the work of Singh and Espejo (2007) and modified a class chain ratio-product type estimator $\bar{y}_{RP}^{(dc)}$ for estimating population mean \bar{Y} using two auxiliary characters under two conditions in Singh and Espejo (2007). The modified estimator, its bias and MSE are respectively given as

$$\bar{y}_{RP}^{(dc)} = \bar{y} \left[k \frac{\bar{x}_1}{\bar{x}} \frac{\bar{Z}}{\bar{z}_1} + (1-k) \frac{\bar{x}}{\bar{x}_1} \frac{\bar{z}_1}{\bar{Z}} \right] \quad (2.14)$$

Subramani and Prabavathy (2014) modified two estimators of population mean based on median of study variable using auxiliary information as:

$$\bar{y}_{SP1} = \bar{y} \left[\frac{M_d M + \bar{X}}{M_d m + \bar{X}} \right] \quad (2.35)$$

$$\bar{y}_{SP2} = \bar{y} \left[\frac{\bar{X} M + M_d}{\bar{X} m + M_d} \right] \quad (2.36)$$

where M , M_d and m are Median of the study variable, Median of the auxiliary variable and Sample median of study variable respectively.

The MSEs of modified estimators are given below;

$$MSE(\bar{y}_{SPi}) = \text{var}(\bar{y}) + R_m^2 \phi_i^2 \text{var}(m) - 2R_m \phi_i \text{cov}(\bar{y}, m) \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (2.37)$$

where $R_m = \bar{Y} / M$, $\phi_1 = MM_d / (MM_d + \bar{X})$ and $\phi_2 = \bar{X} M / (\bar{X} M + M_d)$.

Singh (2015) modified an improved class of ratio type estimator for finite population mean using unknown weight and power transformation strategies. The particular cases of this estimator are Walsh (1970) estimator at $k = 1$ and $\alpha = w$, Ray et al., (1979) estimator at

$k = -1$ and $\alpha = -\gamma$, Srivenkataramana and Tracy (1979) at $k = -1$ and $\alpha = 1 - f$, Srivenkataramana and Tracy (1979) at $k = -1$ and $\alpha = -n / (N - n)$ and Srivenkataramana (1980) at $k = -1$ and $\alpha = 1 - w$. The modified estimator and its properties are given below;

$$\bar{y}_{RVK} = \bar{y} \left[\frac{\sqrt{\bar{X}}}{\alpha\sqrt{\bar{x}} + (1-\alpha)\sqrt{\bar{X}}} \right]^k \quad (2.38)$$

$$Bias(\bar{y}_{RVK}) = \bar{Y} \frac{1-f}{n} \left[\left(\frac{k(k+1)}{4} \alpha^2 + \frac{1}{8} k\alpha \right) C_x^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\alpha\rho_{xy} C_x C_y \right] \quad (2.39)$$

$$MSE(\bar{y}_{RVK}) = \bar{Y}^2 \frac{1-f}{n} \left[C_y^2 + \frac{1}{4} k^2 \alpha^2 C_x^2 - k\alpha\rho_{xy} C_x C_y \right] \quad (2.40)$$

In his study, the modified estimators attain the optimality when $\alpha k = 2\rho_{xy} C_y / C_x$. The empirical study of in his work revealed that the modified estimator is more efficient than the estimators of Walsh (1979), Ray *et al.*, (1979), Srivenkataramana and Tracy (1979), Srivenkataramana (1980).

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Robust Outlier-Free Measure to be used in the Study

The study will utilize robust, outlier-resistant parameter estimation techniques to minimize or eliminate the influence of extreme values in the sample data. These methods include:

- i. Gini's Mean Difference method
- ii. Downton's Method
- iii. The Method of Probability-Weighted Moments

3.1.1 Gini's Mean Method

Let $\Delta_{xi} = X_{(i+1)} - X_{(i)}$, where $X_{(i)}$ is the order statistics so that $\Delta_{xi}, i = 1, \dots, n-1$ is the distance between adjacent observations. Then Gini's mean method proposed by Nair (1936) is given as

$$G = \frac{4}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{2i-n-1}{2n} \right) X_{(i)} \quad (3.1)$$

3.1.2 Downton's Method

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , be a random sample from a normal distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 ; that is, $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$. Let $X_{(1)} \leq X_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq X_{(n)}$ denote the corresponding order statistics. The Downton estimator, D proposed by Downton (1966), is given as

$$D = C \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(2i-n-1)X_{(i)}}{n(n-1)} \quad (3.2)$$

Where $C = \sqrt{\pi} = 1.772453851$ for a normal distribution and does not depend on the sample size n .

3.1.3 Method of probability weighted moments

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , be a random sample from a normal distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 ; that is, $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$. Let $X_{(1)} \leq X_{(2)} \leq \dots X_{(n)}$ denote the corresponding order statistics. The PWMs is defined by Greenwood *et al.* (1979) and is given as

$$S_{pw} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n (2i - n - 1) X_{(i)} \tag{3.3}$$

4.0 Data Analysis and Discussion of result

For empirical validation, four simulated population datasets with varying sampling conditions were generated to assess the performance of the proposed estimators within Survey Sampling. Their efficiency was evaluated against existing estimators using Bias, Mean Square Error (MSE), and Percentage Relative Efficiency (PRE), which measure accuracy, variability, and relative performance in estimating the population mean. Bias and MSE assessed closeness to true parameters and estimation precision, while PRE enabled comparative efficiency analysis, providing a systematic framework that demonstrates the effectiveness and potential superiority of the proposed estimators within Statistics.

4.1 Populations used for Simulation Study for positive relationship

Table 1: Biases, MSEs and PREs of Existing Estimators and Proposed Estimators of the proposed schemes 1, 2 and 3 using N=2000, $n_1=800$, $n=300$, $r=200$ (Case 1 & 2)

Estimators	Case 1			Case 2		
	Biases	MSEs	PREs	Biases	MSEs	PREs
Sample mean T_0	0.00974	0.029	100.0000	0.00016	0.0298	100
Lee <i>et al.</i> (1994) T_1	-0.00107	0.0102	284.2900	-0.00471	0.01019	292.3500
Singh & Horn (2000) T_2	-0.00265	0.00994	291.8400	-0.00543	0.01088	273.8100
Kadilar & Cingi (2008) T_3	0.01267	0.02634	110.1000	0.02825	0.04539	65.6500
Singh (2009) T_4	0.00133	0.01002	289.5600	0.00058	0.01134	262.8300

<i>Audu et al. (2021b) T5</i>	-0.02768	0.01163	249.4300	-0.04152	0.01544	192.9900
<i>Musa et al. (2023)</i>						
T6 ($a=Cx, b=Sx$)	-1.08465	1.25058	2.3200	-1.09581	1.26833	2.3500
T6 ($a=Cx, b=Skw$)	-1.18521	1.47997	1.9600	-1.19667	1.50113	1.9800
T6 ($a=Cx, b=Kurt$)	-1.20351	1.52412	1.9000	-1.2151	1.5463	1.9300
T6 ($a=Sx, b=Cx$)	-1.2069	1.5324	1.8900	-1.21852	1.55478	1.9200
T6 ($a=Sx, b=Skw$)	-1.20694	1.53248	1.8900	-1.21855	1.55486	1.9200
T6 ($a=Sx, b=Kurt$)	-1.20916	1.53792	1.8900	-1.22079	1.56043	1.9100
T6 ($a=Skw, b=Sx$)	-1.08394	1.24905	2.3200	-1.09511	1.26679	2.3500
T6 ($a=Skw, b=Cx$)	-1.1847	1.47874	1.9600	-1.19615	1.49987	1.9900
T6 ($a=Skw, b=Kurt$)	-1.20344	1.52395	1.9000	-1.21502	1.54612	1.9300
T6 ($a=Kurt, b=Cx$)	-1.13035	1.35207	2.1400	-1.14157	1.37098	2.1700
T6 ($a=Kurt, b=Sx$)	-1.00982	1.09422	2.6500	-1.0211	1.11102	2.6800
T6 ($a=Kurt, b=Skw$)	-1.13097	1.35346	2.1400	-1.14219	1.3724	2.1700
<i>Estimators of Proposed Scheme 1</i>						
Tp11 (G,D)	-0.00293	0.00959	302.3200	-0.00521	0.00993	300.0000
Tp12 (G,S)	-0.00311	0.00965	300.6500	-0.005	0.01024	290.9600
Tp13 (D,G)	-0.00323	0.00972	298.4500	-0.00479	0.01053	282.8800
Tp14 (D,S)	-0.00328	0.00976	297.2700	-0.00468	0.01067	279.2400
Tp15 (S,G)	-0.00303	0.00962	301.6000	-0.0051	0.01009	295.4400
Tp16 (S,D)	-0.0029	0.00959	302.4800	-0.00524	0.00989	301.3200
<i>Estimators of Proposed Scheme 2</i>						
Tp21 (G,D)	0.01144	0.03097	93.6300	0.00188	0.03217	92.6300
Tp22 (G,S)	0.01264	0.0324	89.5200	0.00312	0.0339	87.9000
Tp23 (D,G)	0.01363	0.0336	86.3000	0.00416	0.03538	84.2300
Tp24 (D,S)	0.01407	0.03413	84.9600	0.00461	0.03603	82.6900
Tp25 (S,G)	0.01206	0.0317	91.4700	0.00252	0.03305	90.1500
Tp26 (S,D)	0.01126	0.03075	94.2900	0.0017	0.0319	93.3900
<i>Estimators of Proposed Scheme 3</i>						
Tp31 (G,D)	-0.00219	0.00965	300.5000	-0.00558	0.00934	319.0300
Tp32 (G,S)	-0.0019	0.00974	297.6400	-0.00564	0.00924	322.4900
Tp33 (D,G)	-0.00165	0.00985	294.5000	-0.00566	0.0092	323.9800
Tp34 (D,S)	-0.00154	0.0099	292.9400	-0.00566	0.00919	324.2300
Tp35 (S,G)	-0.00204	0.00969	299.1500	-0.00561	0.00928	321.0400
Tp36 (S,D)	-0.00224	0.00964	300.8400	-0.00557	0.00936	318.3400

Table 2: Biases, MSEs and PREs of Existing Estimators and Proposed Estimators of the proposed schemes 1, 2 and 3 using $N=2000$, $n_1=1000$, $n=500$, $r=300$ (Case 1 & 2)

Estimators	Case 1			Case 2		
	Biases	MSEs	PREs	Biases	MSEs	PREs
Sample mean T_0	-0.00227	0.01853	100	0.00277	0.01875	100
Lee et al. (1994) T_1	-0.00414	0.00423	438.36	-0.00157	0.00645	290.86
Singh & Horn (2000) T_2	-0.00441	0.00407	454.81	-0.00221	0.00685	273.55
Kadilar & Cingi (2008) T_3	0.01484	0.01824	101.6	0.01666	0.02677	70.04
Singh (2009) T_4	-0.00115	0.00411	450.69	0.00135	0.00699	268.38
Audu et al. (2021b) T_5	-0.02433	0.00531	348.68	-0.0247	0.00846	221.71
Musa et al. (2023)						
T_6 ($a=Cx, b=Sx$)	-0.99812	1.02416	1.81	-0.97778	0.99538	1.88
T_6 ($a=Cx, b=Skw$)	-1.12083	1.28358	1.44	-1.1005	1.25366	1.5
T_6 ($a=Cx, b=Kurt$)	-1.14291	1.33356	1.39	-1.12257	1.30354	1.44
T_6 ($a=Sx, b=Cx$)	-1.14699	1.34293	1.38	-1.12666	1.31289	1.43
T_6 ($a=Sx, b=Skw$)	-1.14703	1.34303	1.38	-1.1267	1.31299	1.43
T_6 ($a=Sx, b=Kurt$)	-1.14971	1.34918	1.37	-1.12938	1.31913	1.42
T_6 ($a=Skw, b=Sx$)	-0.99725	1.02243	1.81	-0.97691	0.99367	1.89
T_6 ($a=Skw, b=Cx$)	-1.12021	1.28219	1.45	-1.09988	1.25227	1.5
T_6 ($a=Skw, b=Kurt$)	-1.14282	1.33337	1.39	-1.12249	1.30334	1.44
T_6 ($a=Kurt, b=Cx$)	-1.05418	1.13884	1.63	-1.03384	1.10943	1.69
T_6 ($a=Kurt, b=Sx$)	-0.90522	0.84804	2.18	-0.88493	0.82079	2.28
T_6 ($a=Kurt, b=Skw$)	-1.05493	1.14042	1.62	-1.03459	1.111	1.69
Estimators of Proposed Scheme 1						
T_{p11} (G,D)	-0.00472	0.00392	472.18	-0.00221	0.00697	268.78
T_{p12} (G,S)	-0.00462	0.00402	460.55	-0.0021	0.00726	258.38
T_{p13} (D,G)	-0.00452	0.00414	447.8	-0.00198	0.00752	249.15
T_{p14} (D,S)	-0.00446	0.0042	441.54	-0.00193	0.00765	245.03
T_{p15} (S,G)	-0.00467	0.00397	466.73	-0.00216	0.00711	263.53
T_{p16} (S,D)	-0.00473	0.00391	473.57	-0.00223	0.00694	270.31
Estimators of Proposed Scheme 2						
T_{p21} (G,D)	-0.00096	0.0203	91.26	0.00419	0.02055	91.22
T_{p22} (G,S)	-0.00002	0.0216	85.78	0.00524	0.02188	85.67
T_{p23} (D,G)	0.00079	0.02271	81.58	0.00614	0.02303	81.4
T_{p24} (D,S)	0.00114	0.0232	79.85	0.00654	0.02354	79.63
T_{p25} (S,G)	-0.00048	0.02097	88.37	0.00473	0.02123	88.3
T_{p26} (S,D)	-0.00111	0.02011	92.15	0.00404	0.02035	92.12

<i>Estimators of Proposed Scheme 3</i>						
Tp31 (G,D)	-0.00481	0.00389	476.51	-0.00237	0.00645	290.58
Tp32 (G,S)	-0.00477	0.00396	467.51	-0.00233	0.00637	294.16
Tp33 (D,G)	-0.00471	0.00406	456.56	-0.00226	0.00635	295.35
Tp34 (D,S)	-0.00468	0.00411	450.95	-0.00222	0.00635	295.36
Tp35 (S,G)	-0.00479	0.00392	472.48	-0.00235	0.0064	292.72
Tp36 (S,D)	-0.00481	0.00388	477.45	-0.00237	0.00647	289.82

4. 2 Interpretation of the Results

The interpretation of the simulation results is carried out based on the key aims of the proposed modifications, namely the reduction of bias, minimization of Mean Square Error (MSE), and improvement in efficiency in estimating the population mean within Survey Sampling. To evaluate the performance of the proposed estimators with respect to these objectives, simulation data were generated and analyzed under different sampling configurations. The results obtained from the simulation study are summarized in Tables 1–2 for Cases 1 and 2.

These tables present the computed values of Biases, Mean Square Errors (MSEs), and Percentage Relative Efficiencies (PREs) of the proposed class of estimators and compare them with those of several existing estimators developed by Lee *et al.* (1994) T_1^* , Singh and Horn (2000) T_2^* , Kadilar and Cingi (2008) T_3^* , Singh (2009) T_4^* , Audu *et al.* (2021b) $T_{5(j)}^*$, $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and Musa *et al.* (2023) $T_{6(j)}^*$, $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Through these comparisons, the effectiveness of the modified regression-cum-dual mean imputation estimators is assessed in terms of their ability to produce estimates with smaller bias, lower MSE, and higher efficiency relative to the existing estimators. The subsequent interpretation therefore examines the results in relation to

each modification aim in order to demonstrate the statistical advantages of the proposed estimators within the framework of Statistics.

5.0 Conclusion

This study examined the statistical properties of the proposed modified estimators for estimating the population mean in the presence of non-response within the framework of Survey Sampling. The analytical properties of the estimators, particularly their Biases and Mean Square Errors (MSEs), were derived up to the third-order approximation using the Taylor Series Expansion. These derivations provided a theoretical basis for evaluating the performance of the modified imputation estimators and for establishing conditions under which they outperform some existing estimators considered in the study.

Furthermore, the efficiency conditions of the modified estimators were obtained by comparing the minimum MSE expressions of the proposed estimators with the MSE (or minimum MSE) expressions of the competing estimators. The bias and MSE expressions of the proposed imputation schemes were derived using binomial expansion techniques up to the third order, which allowed for a more accurate approximation of the estimators' sampling properties. This analytical framework enabled the determination of efficiency conditions and provided insight into the circumstances under which the proposed estimators yield improved estimation performance.

In addition to the theoretical derivations, an empirical study based on simulated data was conducted to further evaluate the performance of the modified estimators. The simulation results confirmed the theoretical findings, demonstrating that the proposed estimators

consistently exhibit smaller biases, lower MSEs, and higher Percentage Relative Efficiencies (PREs) when compared with the existing estimators. Overall, the results of both the theoretical analysis and the simulation study indicate that the proposed imputation estimators provide more accurate and efficient estimates of the population mean, thereby offering a useful methodological contribution to Statistics in handling missing data under two-phase sampling designs.

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